

APPARENT ELASTIC MODULUS OF POLYETHYLENE AND ITS NANOCOMPOSITES MEASURED AT DIFFERENT SCALES

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INTRODUCTION

Graphene/Graphite Nanoplatelets (GNPs)

Fullerene

Nanotube

Graphite

Nanoplatelets

Strength (MPa)
Stiffness (GPa)
Thermal conductivity (W/K.m)
Electrical conductivity (S/cm)

Graphene	Ref.
130000	350 (steel)
1000	200 (steel)
4000	400 (silver)
6000	70% > silver

Kumar, A., Sharma, K. & Dixit, A.R. A review on the mechanical properties of polymer composites reinforced by carbon nanotubes and graphene. Carbon Lett. 31, 149–165 (2021).

Agglomeration Challenges

Kornmann, X. (2001). Synthesis and characterisation of thermoset-layered silicate nanocomposites (Doctoral dissertation, Luleå tekniska universitet).

Real composite is a mixture of all of the above!
Challenging to predict the properties at this scale

OBJECTIVES

- How can we best characterize nanocomposites?
- How valid is the different techniques at different scales? How do they compare? Which is the most representative?
- What are advantages and disadvantages of each of those techniques?

METHODOLOGY

GNP Masterbatch

Masterbatch

35 wt% GNP
40 layers
50 μm lateral size
20 nm thickness

High density Polyethylene
(HDPE)

GNPs

Functional groups
OH, C=O

Commercial product

Recyclable

Stable production

Suitable form for industry

Less hazardous

Melt Compounding

Advantages

- Upscaling possibility
- Use of masterbatch
- No process modification
- Environmentally friendly
- Solvent free

Limitations

- High viscosity of the melt
- High percolation threshold
- Limited to short fibers

Tests at Different Scales

Tensile test (macro)

Instron 3366
Displacement control test
2mm/min

Nano-indentation (meso/micro)

NanoTest Vantage
10 mN max load
15 sec loading time
Berkovitch indenter

ImAFM (Nano)

A Bruker Dimension Icon AFM
ImAFM mode
Frequencies near resonance
TAP300 DLC Probe

ImAFM

(a) The linear response of the resonator away from the surface. When driven with two frequencies, f_1 and f_2 , the linear system responds with oscillation at f_1 and f_2 .

(b) When close to the surface, nonlinear tip-surface interactions generate IMPs of many orders.

RESULTS

Comparison of results at the different scales

Apparent Modulus (GPa)			
	Tension	NI	ImAFM
LDPE	0.42	0.71	0.42-1.1
LDPE4	0.79	0.71	0.9
HDPE	1.89	1.84	2.7
HDPE2	2.11	3.46	3.3
GNPs	4.79*	22.6*	~4

* Calculated using micromechanics

Tensile test

- Can obtain more than one property (modulus, strength, Poisson's ratio, etc.)
- More averaged/homogenized value useful for material selection for application (on the final stage of materials development)
- Limitation – require large amount of material to produce statistically representative results

Nano-indentation

- Relatively small samples – good for materials under development
- Could do large number of indents in relatively short time for statistics
- Limitations – more complicated sample preparation routines, expensive equipment, viscoelastic effect (VE-effect)
- Needing to know Poisson's ratio to evaluate the modulus (in

Oliver Pharr model)

$$\frac{1}{E_r} = \frac{1 - \nu_m^2}{E_m} + \frac{1 - \nu_i^2}{E_i}$$

VE-effect in NI

Indents disappear with time for materials exhibiting higher VE

Evaluating stiffness based on other missing properties of particle

ImAFM

- Can resolve microstructure of polymer as well
- Affected by surface freshness (presence of oligomers)
- Working in the scale of reinforcement
- Quantitative output together with image of mapped property
- Relatively less demanding surface preparation (compared to NI)

Conclusions

- Characterization has been performed at the different scales and ImAFM seems to be good complementary technique in the development stage of material.
- ImAFM gives reasonable values of the effective modulus of particles that could be used for modelling
- Nano-indentation gives values depending on the indented area and requires wider pre-knowledge of the material
- All techniques fail to predict or solve the problem at higher concentrations due to interaction between the particles

THANK YOU FOR
LISTENING

For details related to ImAFM contact
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The logo for Luleå University of Technology, featuring a large, stylized white letter 'L' on the right side of the text.